

STUDIES ON BEHAVIOURAL PATTERN OF ADULT CAMEL IN DIFFERENT SYSTEMS OF MANAGEMENT

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ABSTARCT

Seven adult female camels (6 to 7 year age) were selected and kept in switch over design in two different systems of management like loose housing (L.H.) and semi-intensive system (S.I.) for two months. Different behavioural patterns exhibited by camels were recorded throughout the period. The analysis of data revealed that total average time involved in feed intake was more (327.53±2.92 min.) in S.I. condition than L.H. condition. The total average time involved in rumination was more in S.I. (439.78 min.) than L.H. (422.78 min.) system. The nocturnal rumination time is maximum as compared to day time rumination in both systems of management. The total average time involved in sleeping is more in S.I. than L.H. condition. The total average time for idling was less in S.I. than L.H. condition. The total average frequency of defecation and urination of adult camel were more in night than day time in all systems of management. The total average frequency of agonistic behaviour of camel were less in S.I. than L.H. condition. The study concludes that due to higher time involvement in feeding and other related activities and less time involvement in idling like activity semi-intensive system is better than intensive system for adult camel management.

INTRODUCTION

Camel rearing enterprise fits well with desert ecosystem. The camel has unique adaptive characteristics for survivability in the harsh conditions. It has been estimated that a well-fed camel can carry some six months energy on its back while cattle are unlikely to have more than 2-3 months, if run out of food (Khanna, 1986). Therefore camel can tolerate high temperature, solar radiation, water deprivation and subsists on poor quality thorny vegetation. The total world camel population is estimated to be 19.32 million of which India has of 1.03 million (FAO, 2002). Heifer project International, a private non-profit development agency is assisting tribal minorities who seek gainful employment by using camel (Robert et al., 1997). Evaluation of IRDP in arid lands has indicated that average increase in income of beneficiaries was one of the highest among people who has given loan for purchase of camel (Khanna, 1994). Since 85% of the gross cultivated area of Bikaner district is non-irrigated, camel hold a significant potential for financing (Amresh Kumar, 1999). It is therefore necessary to investigate the behavioural pattern of camel under different management systems to introduce ideal management practices appropriate to ecosystems and traditions applicable to specific region for economic up keep of camels.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Seven adult female camel (Bikaneri breeds), around 6 to 7 years of age were selected from the NRCC herd. They were kept in switch over design in two different systems of management like Loose Housing (L.H.)/Intensive (I) system and Semi-intensive system (S.I.) for two months viz., (1) Loose Housing/Intensive system : In this system all camels were kept in the open type of shed which was provided with 1.5 meter high wire fencing. The fence was supported by iron angle. Some Kikar trees (*Prosopis Juliflora*) were there to provide the shade. Each camel was provided with 40-45 meter square spaces and a common feeding manger with 75cm breath and 40 cm depth (internal dimension). The floor was kachcha with loose sand dune. The soiled sand of the floor was replaced with new sand wheifftluired. (2) Semi-

intensive system: In this system all the camels were daily sent to range land area for grazing/ browsing for about 6 hr (10.00 am to 4.00 pm) and offered dry fodder in evening after return from field. Ad-labium water was provided to each group once in a day. The DM of feed samples was determined by drying the sample in a hot air oven at $99\pm 1^{\circ}\text{C}$ temperature for overnight.

Behavioural Patterns: Different behavioural patterns exhibited by camels were observed throughout the 24 hours period. The observation on the feeding behaviour started at 6.00 A.M. and completed at 6.00 A.M. on the subsequent days. Thus, a day was considered from 6.00 A.M. to 5.59 P.M. and a night from 6.00 P.M. to 5.59 A.M. of next day. The observations were recorded for seven complete days in a month in each group. Different behavioural patterns of camel were recorded at 15 minutes interval in a special type of score card developed for this purpose. The hour-wise observations were decoded with the help of decoding sheet. Total time spent for every activity in each hour was cumulated and frequency of defecation, urination, drinking and fighting were counted. The suitable statistical methods (Snedecor and Cochran, 1989) were applied to analyse data.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The Mean $\pm$ SE of different behavioural pattern of adult camel in 24 hours is presented in Table 1. The total average time involved in feed intake (TF) was more (327.53 ± 2.92 min.) in S.I. system than L.H. condition because camel were getting an opportunities of browsing (BR) and grazing (GR). The percent time involved in feed intake was 20.17% in L.H. and 22.75% in S.I. condition. The time taken for feed intake was maximum during day as compared to night in both system of management. During day total time involved in feed intake was 18.35% in L.H. and 21.01% in S.I. condition whereas values were 1.82% in L.H. and 1.74% in S.I. system during night. It was suggested that in loose housing system the fodder supplied at 10.00 A.M. in sufficient quantity is enough for the daily requirements of camels. There is no need to employ any labour after 11.00 A.M. for looking after the feeding job. Bhakat (1997) found that housing management systems significantly ($P<0.01$) affect the average fodder and concentrate intake in female goats. The total average time involved in rumination was more in S.I. (439.78 min.) than L.H./I (422.78 min.) systems. The nocturnal rumination is maximum as compared to day time rumination in both systems of management. During night total rumination time was 22.18% in S.I. and 21.45% in L.H./I condition. The rumination activity was more in lying than standing posture during day and night in both system of management. The time involved in rumination in S.I. condition was 7.64% and 22.90% in standing and lying posture, respectively. Whereas in L.H. condition it was 7.12% and 22.24% in standing and lying posture, respectively. The rumination time gradually increased with advancement of age of the animals. This may be due to advancement of age, rumen became well developed, the body weight of camels gradually increased and with that the feed requirement was also increased. To fulfill more feed requirement, camels consumed more DM which lead to increment of rumination time. The total average time involved in sleeping (SP) is more in S.I. condition (125.43 ± 1.23 min.) than L.H. (98.75 ± 0.84 min.) because camel were getting much more physical exercise in S.I. condition than L.H. and to fulfill the normal physiological needs they devote more time in sleeping. The nocturnal sleeping is maximum as compared to day time in both system of management. It was during night 8.17% and 6.26% in S.I. and L.H. conditions, respectively. Whereas during day it was 0.54% and 0.60% in S.I. and L.H. condition respectively.

Table 1. Mean±SE of different behavioural pattern of adult camel in 24 hours

Time	N	Standing posture						Lying posture						Total	
		TF	RU	ID	RO	RU	ID	RU	ID	SP	RU	ID			
LH/ Min/24Hr (%)	49	IF- 290.55±2.26 (20.17)	102.46±1.54 (7.12)	282.37±2.85 (19.61)	60.40±1.86 (4.19)	320.32±2.73 (22.24)	287.05±2.04 (19.93)	98.75±0.84 (6.86)	422.78 (29.36)	569.42 (39.54)					
		IF- 264.30±2.01 (18.35)	25.16±0.47 (1.75)	140.17±1.49 (9.73)	50.15±1.00 (3.48)	88.70±1.12 (6.16)	143.00±1.05 (9.93)	8.52±0.63 (0.60)	113.86 (7.91)	283.17 (19.66)					
		IF- 26.25±0.31 (1.82)	77.30±1.22 (5.37)	142.20±1.51 (9.88)	10.35±0.92 (0.71)	231.62±2.54 (16.08)	144.05±1.26 (10.00)	90.23±0.75 (6.26)	308.92 (21.45)	286.25 (19.88)					
Min/24 Hr	49	GR - 52.36 BR - 221.12 IF - 5.4.05	110.00±1.26	214.13±2.67	115.68±1.93	329.78±2.99	217.45±2.11	125.43±1.23	439.78	431.55					
SI (%) Min/Day	49	T-327.53±2.92 (22.75)	7.64	95.46±0.72 (14.87)	8.03	92.95±0.48 (22.90)	15.10	30.54	29.99						
		GR-52.36 BR-221.12 IF -29.05	27.50±1.01	96.13±1.74	97.59±0.46	7.84±0.12	120.45	193.19							
		Total-302.53±1.62 (21.01)	1.91	6.63	6.45	117.59±1.10	8.36	12.04							
Min/Night (%)	49	IF -25.00±0.28 (1.74)	82.50±0.23 (5.73)	118.67±2.00 (6.24)	19.55±0.27 (1.36)	236.88±2.76 (16.45)	119.86±2.03 (8.32)	391.38 (22.18)	238.36 (16.55)						

IF- Intake fodder from Manger, GR- Grazing, BR- Browsing, (Figure in parenthesis is indicated % value).

The posture of sleep was that of lateral recumbence. Camel were polyphasic in their sleep. A brief naps, then period of activity followed by sleep was the common feature (Tandon *et al.*, 1988). The total average time involved in roaming (RO)/independent individual movement time was maximum in S.I. system (115.68 ± 1.93 min.) than L.H. condition (60.40 ± 1.86 min.) since camel were getting much more open place in S.I. system. In both system of management roaming is maximum during day than night time. During day it was 6.67% and 3.48% in S.I. and L.H. condition, respectively. During night RO time was 1.36% and 0.71% in S.I. and L.H. system, respectively. Camels have a frequent feeding habit which also might have contributed to more roaming time during the day. During extreme season camel prefer less movement in order to minimise the disturbance in body temperature. The idling means when camel involved in no other activities. The total average time for idling (ID) was less in S.I. system (431.55 min.) than L.H. condition (569.42 min) because camels were devoting much more time in feed intake, rumination and other related activities in S.I. systems. Nocturnal idling was maximum as compared to day time in both systems of management. It was 19.88% and 16.55% in L.H. and S.I. conditions, respectively. During day ID was 19.66% and 12.04% in L.H. and S.I. conditions, respectively. Almost same pattern of idling was found in standing and lying posture in all systems of management.

The frequency distribution of eliminative and other behaviour of adult camel in 24 hours are given in Table 2. The data indicates that total average frequency of defecation (DE) and Urination (UR) of adult camel were more in night than day time in L.H. and S.I. conditions. During night time average defecation frequency was 75.04% and 75.00% in L.H. and S.I. systems, respectively. Whereas average Urination frequency was 75.95% and 75.00% in L.H. and S.I. condition, respectively. During day DE frequency was 24.96% and 25.00% in L.H. and S.I. conditions, respectively. Whereas UR frequency was 24.05% and 25.00% in L.H. and S.I. conditions, respectively. The DE and UR frequency was more in S.I. than L.H. condition. This might be due to more DM intake in S.I. system. Highest frequency of defecation was found between 4.00 to 6.00 A.M. and the lowest was found between 6.00 to 8.00 A.M. This results provide information about management practices i.e. the camel keeping place should be cleaned after 8.00 A.M. so that it may remain clean and hygienic for a longer duration of a day. Bhakat *et al.* (2001) reported that the average time taken for excretion of muconium was 32.00 ± 5.64 min. and first urination was 61.50 ± 2.11 min in camel under loose housing system. The total average frequency of agonistic behaviour was less in S.I. ($1.35\% \pm 0.12$) than L.H. condition ($2.09\% \pm 0.11$) because camels were getting much more open space in S.I. condition. According to the advancement of days, among troop of camel a hierarchy was formed which leads to reduction of the frequency of agonistic behaviour in S.I. condition. In L.H. condition this frequency was maximum during group feeding when camels were competing with each other for taking feed for same manger at the same time. The average frequency of agonistic behaviour was maximum during day as compared to night time. It was during day 75.60% and 54.07% in L.H. and S.I. system of management, respectively. The average attempt for drinking was almost similar type in L.H. ($2.12\% \pm 0.19$) and S.I. conditions ($2.78\% \pm 0.22$). The camel mostly attempt for drinking during day in both system of management.

In L.H. and S.I. conditions adult camel involved much time (%) in overall standing posture (SP) than Lying posture (LP) during day (6 A.M. to 6 P.M.) but this situation was almost reverse during night (6 P.M. to 6 A.M.). It indicates that as the daylight/sunlight disappears,

Table 2. Frequency distribution of eliminative and other behaviour of adult camel in 24 hours

System	Time	N	Eliminative		Attempt for drinking	Agoni
			Defecation	Urination		
Loose housing or intensive	Total/24 Hr	49	12.58±0.23	12.47±0.21	2.12±0.19	2.09±0.19
	Day	49	3.14±0.12 (24.96)	3.00±0.12 (24.05)	2.12±0.19	1.58±0.12 (75)
	Night	49	9.44±0.14 (75.04)	9.47±0.13 (75.95)		0.51±0.04 (24)
Semi intensive	Total/24 Hr	49	13.12±0.25	13.56±0.22	2.78±0.22	1.35±0.12
	Day	49	3.28±0.14 (25.00)	3.39±0.12 (25.00)	2.78±0.22	0.73±0.04 (54)
	Night	49	9.84±0.19 (75.00)	10.17±0.14 (75.00)		0.62±0.04 (47)

(Figure in parenthesis is indicated % value).

camel has a tendency to go in lying posture.

CONCLUSION

The study concludes that due to higher time involvement in feeding and other re activities and less time involvement in idling like activity semi-intensive system is better intensive system for adult camel management.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

Authors express sincere thank to PIU (NATP) arid zone for financial support, Di (NRCC) and I/C farm for cooperation to complete this NATP work.

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